

EcoPlastic

Eco conversion of lower grade PET and mixed recalcitrant PET plastic waste into high performing biopolymers.

D6.4 DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

Call: HORIZON-EIC-2021-PATHFINDEROPEN-01
of Action: HORIZON-EIC

Type

Funded by the
European Union

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe EIC Pathfinder programme under grant agreement No 101046758.

European
Innovation
Council

Grant Agreement n°: **101046758**

Project acronym: **EcoPlastiC**

Project name: **Eco conversion of lower grade PET and mixed recalcitrant PET plastic waste into high performing biopolymers**

Start Date/Duration: 1st October 2022 /36 Months

Deliverable n° & Title: **D6.4 Data Management Plan**

Due date: 31/03/2023

Participant responsible: IMGGE

Version	Date	Author	Organisation	Description
1	15/01/2023	Vesna Mandic	IMGGE	First draft
2	27/01/2023	Vesna Mandic	IMGGE	Second draft
3	29/01/2023	Jasmina Nikodinovic Runic	IMGGE	Third draft
4	31/01/2023	Vesna Mandic	IMGGE	Fourth draft version
5	14/02/2023	Kiran Reddy Buddigam	KTH	Fifth version with KTH inputs
6	21/02/2023	Zahra Geraylou	AVE	Sixth version with AVE inputs
7	02/03/2023	Vesna Mandic	IMGGE	Compiled version with KTH and AVE inputs
8	03/03/2023	Jelena Lazic	IMGGE	Version with IMGGE inputs
9	04/03/2023	Barbara Almeida	NOVA	Version with NOVA inputs
10	06/03/2023	Margaret Brennan Fournet	TUS	Version with TUS inputs
11	20/03/2023	Jasmina Nikodinovic Runic	IMGGE	Final draft version

Type of document (Dissemination Level)	
Public	X
Sensitive	
EU Classified	

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Abbreviation list

AAM	Author Accepted Manuscript
APC	Article Processing Charges
AVE	AVECOM NV
CA	Consortium Agreement
CC BY	Creative Commons license, Credit must be given to the creator
CC0	Creative Commons license, Public Domain Dedication
DMP	Data Management Plan
DNA	Deoxyribonucleic acid
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
IMGGE	INSTITUT ZA MOLEKULARNU GENETIKU I GENETICKO INZENJERSTVO ((Institute of Molecular Genetics and Genetic Engineering)
IO	Innovation objective
IP	Intellectual property
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
EEB	EcoPlastiC Executive Board
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FID	Directory Interchange Format
KTH	KUNGLIGA TEKNISKA HÖGSKOLAN ((KTH Royal Institute of Technology)
NDA	Non-disclosure agreement
NOVA	NOVA ID FCT - ASSOCIAÇÃO PARA A INOVAÇÃO E DESENVOLVIMENTO DA FCT (NOVA School of Science and Technology)
OA	Open access
ORCID	Open <u>R</u> esearcher and <u>C</u> ontributor ID
PID	Persistent identifier
PET	Polyethylene therephtalate
PHA	Polyhydroxyalkanoate
PM	Person month
RDM	Research Data Management
TO	Technical objective
TUS	TECHNOLOGICAL UNIVERSITY OF THE SHANNON: MIDLANDS MIDWEST
VoR	Version of Record
WP	Work package

Executive Summary

This document is a deliverable of the EcoPlastiC project (D6.4 data Management Plan), financed under the HORIZON EUROPE program (HORIZON-EIC-2021-PATHFINDEROPEN-01, GA no 101046758). In the preparation of this first version of the DMP, provisions of GA and CA related to open science, principles of responsible research data management, new approaches in open access to scientific publications and other research outputs were used. In addition, this Plan included the recommended open science practices, which are encouraged in the HORIZON EUROPE program, but respecting the specifics of this EIC Pathfinder project and especially its innovative component.

The elaboration and updating of the Plan is covered by WP6, which is led by IMGGE, but it is important to point out at the beginning that in the preparation of this version, and it will be the same approach for every subsequent version, all consortium members actively participated, not only in providing individual information in the tables and Annexes to the document, but also in the definition of procedures and approaches for the responsible data management, which also affect the role of the EEB board.

The DMP is structured in full accordance with the recommended HORIZON EUROPE template, using all relevant HE guides, recommendations of organisations and working groups established by the European Commission for the purposes of RDM and OA, contained in the [literature review](#) at the end of the document. For the implementation of the DMP in this collaborative and innovative EcoPlastiC project, effective and sustainable procedures for continuous and responsible data management on the project were recommended, so several annexes of this DMP are intended for the continuous input of data and information throughout the project. Thus, this Plan is at the same time an implementation guide for RDM (some annexes contain guides and auxiliary tools for EcoPlastiC researchers) and also an important monitoring tool for EEB and consortium members. With such an approach in data management, it will be easier to report on the realisation of the project in the part of data management, and to complete the final version of the DMP (D6.5). The list of Annexes includes:

- [Annex I](#) – EcoPlastiC datasets (to be continuously updated, as separate document)
- [Annex II](#) – FAIR Checklist
- [Annex III](#) – Recommended and selected repositories and databases (to be updated with list of EcoPlastiC selected trusted repositories and databases in the first project year)
- [Annex IV](#) – Disciplinary metadata standards relevant for EcoPlastiC (to be updated with list of EcoPlastiC selected trusted repositories and databases in the first project year)
- [Annex V](#) – Proposed “readme” style of metadata
- [Annex VI](#) – Data availability statement examples
- [Annex VII](#) – EcoPlastiC scientific publications plan (to be continuously updated, as separate document)
- [Annex VIII](#) – Responsible persons for EcoPlastiC data management (to be updated in the first project year, and if necessary in case of change of nominated responsible persons)

The Plan defines in the [Section 1](#) a summary overview of the data that will be collected and generated during the project, their types, formats and approximate scope, as well as potential sources of secondary data available in open repositories, databases, patent databases, etc. In the [Section 2](#), the ways of applying the FAIR principle are described in detail, procedurally and to the extent that it was possible at the very beginning of the project. They will be updated according to the inputs in the first year of the project, and according to the EEB decisions. Special attention is paid to the management of open access for other research outputs, which are presented in [Section 3](#), taking into account the innovative potential of the project and the constraints resulting from it. This part is closely related to the Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan (D6.1), so this section will be updated in the next versions of the Plan. New open science practices in HE, including this DMP, require significant resources for implementation in the project, in terms of human, financial and material resources. In [Section 4](#), an initial tabular overview of the mentioned resources is given, and the ways of their mobilisation for effective and responsible RDM are presented. Research data security and ethical principles are described in [Section 5](#) and [Section 6](#), respectively. At the end of the Plan, an overview of valid national and institutional regulations related to RDM for consortium members is given in [Section 7](#).

Finally, it should be noted that this Plan is part of an overall project management strategy on the EcoPlastiC project, which aims to regulate the management of all research outputs in the entire research cycle, not only during the EcoPlastiC project, but also after its completion, in terms of defining potential users of data and research outputs, their sharing, then which data can be destroyed and which should be permanently stored, and how to ensure safe and long-term preservation of data and their wide visibility, *i.e.* citation.

1. Data Summary

The interdisciplinary nature of the EcoPlastiC project, the proposed methodology for achieving technical, industrial and scientific goals requires a comprehensive approach to a multitude of data and results of previous research in the fields of material science, polymer engineering, enzymology, microbiology, bioengineering and chemical engineering.

The largest volume of generated research data is actually expected in WP2 - Depolymerisation process, and WP3 - Biopolymer production, which mainly represent quantitative and qualitative data obtained from experimental research, described in more detail in the EcoPlastiC proposal. During experimental research, especially in the stages of methodological design and research data analysis, open research data that are connected with published papers in scientific journals (available data section, supplementary material), as well as data deposited in general or domain-specific repositories will be collected, analysed and accordingly re-used. Researchers will abide by the terms of the reuse licence, and cite the original data its creator(s). Preliminarily, the plan is to search the deposited data in the following repositories:

- <https://zenodo.org/>
- <https://europepmc.org/>
- <https://elixir-europe.org/platforms/data/elixir-deposition-databases>
- or by specific search using <https://www.re3data.org/>

With the growing importance of open data as part of the Open Science policy, the search and use of dedicated currently available datasets is planned. One of the following methods/portals/providers will be used for the search:

- <https://datasetsearch.research.google.com/>
- <https://dcu.libguides.com/c.php?g=685032&p=4895939>
- <https://data.europa.eu/data/datasets?locale=en>
- <https://datasetsearch.research.google.com/search?src=0&query=microbiome%20plastics&docid=L2cvMTFzbXZkeGdnOA%3D%3D>

One of the technical objectives of the project (TO1: Provide Benchmark data) includes a comprehensive analysis of the state of the art, but not only within scientific sources, but also a search of patent databases (ESPACE, USPTO, etc.) and a comprehensive market review, in order to define benchmarks. All of this implies a review of existing research data and a decision on their re-use for the needs of the project.

Within the scope of innovation objectives (*IO2: Accelerate the exploitation of the project IP, leading innovation capacity across Europe that can make a difference in the future*), the analysis of the existing IP portfolio, which includes not only patents, but also machine designs and trademarks, will be basis for technology evaluation. All data collected in this way will be used to define the modality of protection of the newly created IP (novel depolymerisation and biological filtration processes, new biopolymers, biopolymer-based product prototypes, etc.) and preparation of the knowledge transfer plan (part of DEC Plan, D6.1 and D6.6) .

In addition to the aforementioned sources of data, partners will rely on data based on experience and know-how in partner IP backgrounds, specified in Attachment 1 of the Partnership Agreement. This includes data from:

- published scientific publications for which they have authorship (data underpinning a scientific publication)
- granted patents (Patent BE1021400, Patent BE1027695, Patent BE1026952 end NL2024582, Patent NL2019733 and BE1025911, Patent NL202032 and EP3512931, or UK Patent Application No. 2116474.4).
- previous and ongoing HORIZON projects (YPACK¹, INGREEN², BIOICEP³ and NewWave⁴), related to specific microbiome collection, isolation and culturing, and microbial protein/PHA material production and formulation.

Types of the data: qualitative and quantitative data from experimental measurements, as raw, abstracted or analysed data; numerical data (datasets, spreadsheets); textual data (protocols, methodological descriptions, laboratory notebooks, field notebooks, documents, reports); programming data (web-based data), spectral data and DNA sequences, mixed media data (image, audio, video) and presentations.

Formats of the data: .dat, .txt, .opj, .xlsx, .csv, .jpg, .png, .bmp, .spc, .fasta, .cmb, .docx, .pdf, .pptx, .html, .avi, .mp4, flac, .zip, PDF/A etc.

EcoPlastiC partners will try to adapt the choice of data format to good open science practice, specific standards accepted by data repositories and research community, in order to facilitate sharing and long-term re-use of data in accordance with FAIR principles. Some data formats will be conditioned by the use of certain software and laboratory equipment, but additional information for such formats will be provided in the readme.txt file: software name, license version, possibly download link if any, installation instructions, etc.).

Several repositories provide lists of preferred formats for successful long-term preservation and re-use. Accordingly, Table 1 shows the recommended formats for the types of data to be generated on the EcoPlastiC project.

Expected size of the data: 1.0 – 1.5 Tb

Generated research data, deposited in appropriate repositories, which are not commercially valuable or after appropriate IP protection, can be re-used by researchers and scientists who will further deal with the EcoPlastiC approach for recycling and the depolymerisation of PET mixed plastic waste and their conversion into new biopolymers. In addition to them, EcoPlastiC open datasets will be relevant to several sectors derived from chemicals and plastics which are characterized by a high dependence on fossil raw materials and energy in their production and processing technologies and are therefore under greater pressure to shift to circular models.

¹ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/773872>

² <https://www.bbi.europa.eu/projects/ingreen>

³ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/870292>

⁴ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101058369>

Table 1. Types and formats of EcoPlastiC research data

Data types	Digital content	Recommended formats	Other acceptable formats
Text	Protocols Documents Reports	Plain text (ASCII, UTF-8, UTF-16 with BOM) Open Office (.odt) Reach text format (.rtf) PDF/A (Archival PDF)	MS Office (.doc, .docx) PDF (.pdf)
Numerical	Datasets Spreadsheets	ASCII or Unicode Comma Separated Values (*.csv) Delimited Text (*.txt) Compressed format ZIP	MS Office (*.xlsx, *.xls)
Experimental data	DNA sequences Spectral data Pre-treatment evaluation FTIR, DSC, TGA SEM micrographs Reports	.fasta, .spc, .cmb .xlsx .jpeg, .png .jpeg, .png .docx, .pdf	
Image	Raster image Micrographs	JPEG/JFIF (.jpg) PNG (.png) PDF/A, TIFF	JPEG/JPEG2000, BMP (.bmp)
Audio/Video	Audio/video recordings, moves etc.	FLAC, AIFF, WAVE M-JPEG2000 AVI (*.avi)	MPEG3 (.mp3) MPEG-4 (*.mp4)
Presentation	Power Point presentations		MS Office (.ppt, .pptx, .pps)

Due to this DMP is a living document, the data summary will be adjusted in following DMP versions according to digital contents that have been produced. This first DMP version includes [Annex I](#) with a preliminary list of datasets to be generated within the EcoPlastiC project, with a short description and open access conditions attached to them. This annex will be a living document, which will be continuously updated during the project, in order to monitor the status of research data management and facilitate the completion of other versions of the DMP, especially the final one.

2. FAIR data

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

All research data, which represent digital content in the formats listed in Table 2, and for which a decision is made that they can be opened (by EcoPlastiC Executive Board - EEB), and for which there is no restriction (data protection rules, privacy, confidentiality, trade secrets, Union competitive interests, security rules, intellectual property rights, etc.), they will be supported by rich metadata in accordance with FAIR principles (See [Annex II](#) – FAIR Checklist). The basic principle for this is to assign a persistent identifier (PID) to the dataset (DOI or Handle). For this purpose, a trusted repositories will be selected that provide automatic PID assignment. Initially, the partners will consider depositing data in the proposed repositories given in [Annex III](#).

Considering the volume of research data that will be generated during the project, internal procedures for data organisation, their distribution among files, file naming and directory organisation, will be applied, in accordance with the DIF (Directory Interchange Format) standard, in order to easily identify and distinguish them. File name will consist of 1 to 80 alphanumeric characters of the UTF-8 set, including underbars (), hyphen (-), period (.), and colon (:). The name should be intuitive enough to be able to deduce what kind of data it refers to. The initial part of the name should contain the project acronym and then the task number, separated by underbars from the rest of the characters in the name. Versions of the files will be marked with two digits in ascending order, starting from 01, within the same calendar year, which is indicated at the end. For example: *EcoPlastiC_T2.4_microbiome_performance_01.2023.dat*. Folders naming and their structure should follow the organisation of files according to work packages (WPs) and deliverables (Dx.y), with sub-folders for each dataset within which files are grouped.

In addition to the above metadata standard, the partners will consider the use of other disciplinary standards, as listed in [Annex IV](#). The decision on the selection of the appropriate metadata standard(s) will be made during the first year of project implementation.

In order to enable secondary users to understand and reuse the data generated within the project, the partners will prepare rich metadata in “readme.txt” style for each dataset that will be open access and that will be the basis for publishing research results. A recommended template for preparing metadata with clarifications is given in [Annex V](#). Dataset metadata will include basic details allowing their discovery from other users (computer or human):

- Title (descriptive title allowing users to identify the general content and purpose);
- Persistent identifier (issued by selected trustworthy, long-term repository);
- Names of creator(s) (name, ORCID, institution, address, email);
- Geographic location of data collection (latitude, longitude, or city, region, country);
- Creation date (YYYY-MM-DD);
- Spatial / temporal coverage;

- Types of files in dataset;
- Metadata standard used (if any);
- Location of data (links to other publicly accessible locations of the data);
- Funding Statement (information about funding sources that supported the collection of the data, *e.g.* The data were generated as part of the research carried out through the EcoPlastiC project, financed under the HORIZON EUROPE program (HORIZON-EIC-2021-PATHFINDEROPEN-01, GA No. 101046758, Oct 2022 – Sep 2025);
- Description – data abstract (brief dataset description with list of all files (or folders, as appropriate for dataset organisation) contained in the dataset, and if important relationship between files);
- Keywords;
- Licenses/restrictions placed on the data (CC BY⁵ or CC0⁶, to the extent constraints are taken into account);
- Related publications (links to publications that cite or use the data);
- Sources (if data derived from another source(s));
- Recommended citation for the dataset (link(s) to accessible location(s) of the data).

Furthermore, any supplementary information and the documentation that can provide understanding of dataset, and provide its re-use, may be included in metadata with details on:

- Methodology used for collection/generation of data
- Sampling procedures,
- Variables, their definitions and units of measurement,
- Experimental conditions
- Instrument- or software-specific information needed to interpret the data,
- Standards and calibration information
- Performed processing and analytical steps,
- Quality-assurance procedures performed on the data.

Finally, it should be borne in mind that specific disciplines and repositories may dictate the content and format of metadata^{7,8}. Taking into account the specificity of interdisciplinary research included in the EcoPlastiC project, in the course of the project it is necessary to define and additionally include other descriptive information in datasets metadata. The OpenAIRE guidelines for data archiving can be used for this purpose⁹.

⁵ <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

⁶ <https://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0/>

⁷ <https://rdamsc.bath.ac.uk/scheme-index>

⁸ <https://fairsharing.org/>

⁹ <https://guidelines.openaire.eu/en/latest/data/index.html>

2.2. Making data accessible

EcoPlastiC will adhere to open science principles under Horizon Europe programme and will partake in open access to research data. Generally, access rights to data will be managed according to the Consortium Agreement. Given that at least 12 scientific publications in high impact journals (open access) are planned for the dissemination of project results within the scientific community, as well as invited talks at 30 scientific conferences, the research data on which the conclusions presented in these papers are based will be deposited in selected trusted repositories, at the latest at the time of publication of the scientific publication. Any earlier disclosure of data will be possible only after the analysis at the consortium level and the decision of the EcoPlastiC Executive Board (EEB), which is in charge of managing knowledge management and protection activities.

Recommended repositories in [Annex III](#) assign globally unique and persistent identifiers, enable the uploading of submitter-specified metadata that are always publicly available and machine readable/interoperable, have a clearly defined licensing policy and the possibility of choosing a license by the submitter. In addition, they have a long-term preservation plan for the archived data. In this Annex, suggestions are given also for disciplinary databases, which can also be used for depositing research data. During the first year of the project, partners will select appropriate trustworthy data repositories for depositing research data in accordance with FAIR principles, which enable among others direct handling of data requests by submitters. In addition to the recommended repositories in Annex III, EcoPlastiC partners will use the following "repository finders" to find domain-specific repositories, as well as to check trustworthiness criteria^{10,11} for responsible decision making:

- **OPENDOAR** - global Directory of Open Access Repositories Search for open repositories (www.opendoar.org)

¹⁰ https://scienceeurope.org/media/4brkxe5/se_rdm_practical_guide_extended_final.pdf

¹¹ **Essential characteristics of trusted repositories** (source: GA):

- display specific characteristics of organisational, technical and procedural quality such as services, mechanisms and/or provisions that are intended to secure the integrity and authenticity of their contents, thus facilitating their use and re-use in the short- and long-term. Trusted repositories have specific provisions in place and offer explicit information online about their policies, which define their services (e.g. acquisition, access, security of content, long-term sustainability of service including funding etc.).
- provide broad, equitable and ideally open access to content free at the point of use, as appropriate, and respect applicable legal and ethical limitations. They assign persistent unique identifiers to contents (e.g. DOIs, handles, etc.), such that the contents (publications, data and other research outputs) are unequivocally referenced and thus citeable. They ensure that contents are accompanied by metadata sufficiently detailed and of sufficiently high quality to enable discovery, reuse and citation and contain information about provenance and licensing; metadata are machine- actionable and standardised (e.g. Dublin Core, Data Cite etc.) preferably using common non-proprietary formats and following the standards of the respective community the repository serves, where applicable.
- facilitate mid- and long-term preservation of the deposited material. They have mechanisms or provisions for expert curation and quality assurance for the accuracy and integrity of datasets and metadata, as well as procedures to liaise with depositors where issues are detected. They meet generally accepted international and national criteria for security to prevent unauthorised access and release of content and have different levels of security depending on the sensitivity of the data being deposited to maintain privacy and confidentiality.

- **RE3DATA** - Repository Finder to facilitate the search for a suitable general or discipline-specific repository for various kinds of research outputs (www.re3data.org).

Considering the innovative character of the project, the results that can be commercially exploited, and for which it is necessary to apply IP protection (patent, NDA, business secret, *etc.*), some datasets must be closed or with restricted access (with assigned contact details for potential users), although the metadata will be licensed under CC0. If the newly generated IP is the result of research in which only one partner institution participated, the decision on the possibility and time of opening the data will be made by that institution, as the owner of the data, in accordance with its legitimate interests and internal procedures. In the event that two or more partners participated in the creation of the IP foreground, then the provisions of the Consortium Agreement will be applied, and everything that is not defined will be the subject of a new Joint IP Ownership and Management Agreement, so that this agreement will define which datasets must be closed and for how long (embargo). More details on this will be presented in the final version of the DMP (D6.5, M36), and in particular:

- procedure for appraising and selecting datasets for long-term preservation
- what data must be retained or destroyed for contractual, legal, or regulatory purposes
- foreseeable research uses (and/ or users) for the data
- what specific tools to access and (re-)use the data are necessary for potential users
- sustainability of software needed for accessing the data.

2.3. Making data interoperable

As previously described and shown in Table 1, data generated on the EcoPlastiC project will be prepared and stored in standard formats generally accepted in the scientific community, which can be easily loaded into available software applications for further use. Vocabulary and methodologies to be used throughout the project will be standardised to enable interoperability.

As for the datasets from experimental investigations, they will mainly represent well-structured tabular numerical data that will be internally stored in XLSX format, but for the purposes of depositing in open repositories, they will be converted into machine-readable (also actionable) CSV (Comma Separated Value) format. This is only possible if each spreadsheet file is prepared appropriately. In this regard, the following approach will be applied:

- each column will have a descriptive heading in single row
- each worksheet will start from the first cell A1
- each spreadsheet will have a title and a legend
- each worksheet is a separate file to be deposited within dataset
- non-alphanumeric characters, including commas, will not be used
- spreadsheet does not have merged cells and colour coding
- any chart, comment or other tables will be excluded from the spreadsheet

Other research data, which are not of numerical type, will be prepared in also machine-readable formats, in accordance with the standards, namely: RDF, XML or JSON. Most repositories allow checking and help in preparing data in the above-mentioned formats, so this criterion will also be taken into account when choosing a trusted repository. In addition, they already have elaborated approaches for defining the semantic model, recommendations for preparing relations in the datasets, or for connecting different datasets, in a machine-actionable way¹². If it is determined that some research data in the dataset are not linkable (not completely FAIR), they will be transformed by applying Semantic Web technology or Linked Data technology. Although it is initially planned to prepare the metadata in the "readme" style, if the request for depositing in a specific repository is more interoperability, it can be prepared with appropriate support in the RDF format (machine-actionable format).

When certain data in the dataset is based on other data as qualified references (from previous projects and research, and which have assigned PIDs), it is planned to link the dataset with those references through their citation via PID. Cited references will be listed in the metadata description and their scientific link/relation with the EcoPlastiC dataset will be described.

2.4. Increase data re-use

The proposed structure of datasets metadata (see Section 2.1) includes additional information related to research methodology, sampling, experimental conditions, variables, units of measurement, as well as procedures for processing and analysing experimental data, which enables validation of the conducted analysis and displayed results, as well as re-use of the data. The metadata will be licensed under the Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication License (CC0¹³) in accordance with GA provisions, while the datasets to which the metadata refers could be even closed or restricted based on a thorough check of all possible restrictions, bearing in mind the innovative nature of the IP foreground.

Open research data will be licensed with the latest version of a Creative Commons Attribution International Public License (CC BY¹⁴) requiring attribution of authorship, except in the case of large datasets whose re-use would be problematic with such a license, where the CC0 license will be applied, if the authors of the datasets agree with it. The provenance of the data will be systematically documented in metadata.

Data deposited by EcoPlastiC partners in open repositories can be used by third parties (researchers, companies, others) under the conditions specified in the license (CC BY or CC0). All published scientific papers (at least 12) in journals and conference proceedings (at least 30) will contain a *Data Availability Statement*, with information where the data associated with the paper is available (open data repository, link and PID), and under what conditions the data can be accessed (details of any restrictions on accessing the data and a justifiable explanation, e.g. for ethical, legal or commercial reasons). Examples of these statements are given in [Annex VI](#) for a number of scenarios that may occur during the project. In cases where the data generated during the project are linked to exploitable results but there is a possibility of access on request by third party only, the authors of the paper will provide a contact email address. It

¹² Zenodo uses [JSON Schema](#) as internal representation of metadata and offers export to other popular formats such as [Dublin Core](#) or [MARCXML](#).

¹³ <https://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0/>

¹⁴ <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

should be emphasised that this DMP will be a living document throughout the project's runtime and will be adapted whenever appropriate.

Data quality assurance will be provided using standardised procedures that will consist of device calibration, repeated samples or measurements, standardised data capture, data entry validation and peer review of data. Each researcher and project partner will be familiar with these procedures at the beginning of the project implementation.

3. Other research outputs

The transparency of the research process and outputs is the way to greater citations, which is important for researchers but also for the reputation of companies, however, it depends to a large extent on how complete the output is, whether it is fully documented, where it is stored and how it is shared. Since during the EcoPlastiC project, in addition to the generation of data during experimental research, significant research outputs will be produced, it is necessary to foresee the ways and conditions of their sharing in this plan, in accordance with of the GA requirements. It is common that they can be shared months or years after data generation, and that some processes are time-consuming (*e.g.* publication of paper in high-impact scientific journals, patent application approval etc.) therefore, in this version of DMP, only draft plan will be given. Every research project in which breakthrough technologies are developed and innovations are planned has certain uncertainties and risks, so it is difficult to predict when the innovation will be completed as a result, *i.e.* when its protection will allow sharing through patent databases or in some other way.

According to the EcoPlastiC proposal, it is possible in this version of the DMP and at this moment, at the very beginning of the project, to give a preliminary plan for management of research outputs (except for the data and datasets that were previously elaborated), and especially whether and in what way they can be prepared in accordance with the FAIR principles, so that a third party can find, access and re-use them. Regardless of the type of research output, EcoPlastiC partners will strive to ensure that each of them, which is not confidential due to legal interest, IP protection or commercial exploitation limitations, has a unique persistent identifier (PID) or similar digital identifier/tool that allow unique citations for the entire output, or for its elements that may be cited separately.

EcoPlastiC research outputs can be classified into several categories, for which the same or similar “fairification” preparing methods can be defined: new materials, experimental protocols, confidential know-how, demonstrators, patents, scientific publications, position papers, recommendations, presentations, etc. Table 2 shows the basic principles for sharing of EcoPlastiC research outputs. In the next version of DMP (M18 or M36) this table will be updated with more concrete information.

Table 2 – Research outputs sharing approach

EcoPlastiC research outputs	Type	Sharing preparation tools	Sharing via
Research-grade PHA biopolymers	New material	Restricted for sharing as an important aspect of the patent claim(s)	
Optimized aerobic and anaerobic microbiomes	New material		
Channelling of waste into biopolymer (PHA)	Protocol or confidential know-how	Restricted for sharing as an important aspect of the patent claim(s)	
Greener route for PHA production/extraction	Protocol or confidential know-how		
Recycling technology - Mixed waste PET	EcoPlastiC innovation	Patent application Patent	Patent database

Plastics Feedstock Stream Processing)			
Lab Scale Modular demonstrator (profile extrusion, blown film extrusion, thermoforming and injection moulding, cast film and vacuum forming)	Demonstrator (pre-prototypes as high-potential industrial PHA-based products)	prototype	Physical access - meeting
High performance Eco-Plastics blends and multilayers for food packaging applications	New eco-plastics as product	Patent application Patent	Patent database
Prolonged mechanical recyclable PHA-based plastics	New eco-plastics as product	Patent application Patent	Patent database
12 Scientific papers	Publications	Writing paper Fairification of research data Preparing metadata Searching OA publisher Paper submitting Negotiation with OA publisher Searching trusted repository Preparing for deposition of publications and research data	Open access journals Trusted repositories EcoPlastiC website (if no embargo)
Papers in conference proceedings	Publications or presentations	Writing of paper Preparing presentation Choose appropriate conferences and apply	Conference proceedings EcoPlastiC website Horizon Europe Results platform
Position papers, policy and regulatory recommendations	Project documents	Writing papers Writing recommendations Identify stakeholders and target groups for sharing	Open repositories EcoPlastiC website Stakeholders' websites Horizon Europe Results platform
Communication materials for public audience	Annual newsletters, blog posts, YouTube videos, flyers, press releases	- Ecoplastic design identity - preparing communication materials - sharing communication materials among public community	EcoPlastiC website EcoPlastiC partners' websites YouTube Social media (LinkedIn, Twitter, Wiki) Youris.com, Project events International conferences, Researcher's Night, Science fairs, School visits, Student placement, Laboratory tours, Conventional newspapers, TV and radio,

All 12 peer-reviewed scientific papers will be immediately open access at publication time by depositing in a selected trusted repositories (in a machine-readable format), with open CC BY licenses. Also, the research data that is the basis for validating the conclusions in the publication will also be deposited in a trusted repository and linked to the publication in the *Data Availability* section. Additionally, PIDs (DOI or Handle) will be assigned for the publication and research data underlying publication (datasets), and ORCID identifiers will be listed for each author.

Peer-reviewed scientific manuscripts (author accepted manuscript (AAM), or version of record (VoR)) will be published mainly selected open access journals by choosing one of two options: "Green" or "Gold". When choosing a journal for publishing papers and checking the journal's open access status, as well as the existence of embargoes, authors will use the following online resources:

- Sherpa Romeo, an online resource that aggregates and analyses publisher open access policies (<http://www.sherpa.ac.uk/romeo/index.php>) or
- Directory of Open Access Journals (www.doaj.org) or
- Journal Checker Tool (<https://journalcheckertool.org/>).

Publishing in hybrid OA journals¹⁵ is possible, but in that case APC fees will not be paid from the project budget. This is not the case for publication in mirror/sister OA journals¹⁶.

Finally, EcoPlastiC researchers can publish scientific papers in high-impact traditional subscription journals, where in accordance with the provisions of the GA they must retain sufficient IP rights related to the license (CC BY) and the obligation of immediate open access in trusted repository without embargo (for one version of the manuscript, AAM or VoR). In case there is an embargo on the published version, or some other contradiction in relation to GA requirements, the authors will negotiate with the publisher¹⁷, stating the following argumentation:

"This work was funded by the European Union under the Horizon programme, EvoPlastiC project (HORIZON-EIC-2021-PATHFINDEROPEN-01). As set out in the Grant Agreement no 101046758, beneficiaries must ensure that at the latest at the time of publication, open access is provided via a trusted repository to the published version or the final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication under the latest available version of the Creative Commons Attribution International Public Licence (CC BY) or a licence with equivalent rights".

In all cases of publication of scientific papers, in full open access journals, hybrid/sister journals or subscription journals, EcoPlastiC authors will deposit peer-reviewed scientific publications and underlying research data in selected trusted repositories, in a machine-readable format, and in accordance with FAIR

¹⁵ **Hybrid journals** provide part of their scholarly content in open access, while another part is accessible through subscriptions/payments. Specifically, hybrid journals and hybrid books are those journals/books based on subscription/purchase that provide open access to part of their content when an open access fee is paid by their authors/institutions (paid ad hoc or on the basis of an institutional agreement with the publishers).

¹⁶ **Mirror and sister journals** are more recently established open access versions of existing subscription journals. They may share the same editorial board as the original journal and usually have the same or very similar aims, scope and peer review processes and policies. These journals often have a name similar to the subscription title but a different ISSN. In the context of Horizon Europe, they are considered open access publishing venues and not hybrid journals.

¹⁷ <https://www.coalition-s.org/rights-retention-strategy/>

principles, at the latest at the time of publication, while respecting all GA requirements related to licenses, metadata and data validation. Apart from the selected trusted repositories listed in [Annex III](#) of this DMP, researchers will consider the possibility of publishing on Open Research Europe (ORE) open access publishing platform of the European Commission (<https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/>).

The modalities described above for the publication of scientific papers and the author's obligations for each of the OA routes, and related to the provisions of the GA in this Horizon Europe project, are shown schematically in the Figure 1. Other written types of research outputs (papers in conference proceedings, position papers, policy and regulatory recommendations, including this DMP) will also be in open access, primarily on the EcoPlastiC website, the Horizon Europe Results platform and other appropriate open platforms intended for special target groups and stakeholders.

Figure 1. HORIZON EUROPE open access mandate

(Source: <https://www.openaire.eu/how-to-comply-with-horizon-europe-mandate-for-publications>, <https://zenodo.org/record/6641829#.Y9arQq3MJpk>)

In the event that the research results that are planned to be published may threaten the eventual patentability or be contrary to any of the previously mentioned restrictions, the methods of IP protection (patent application or other) will be considered first, and then the paper will be approved to be sent to the editorial of the journal or for presentation on scientific conference. In this connection, researchers

working on the project who do not have clearly defined non-disclosure rules through their Work Contract will sign an NDA (Non-disclosure Agreement). The EcoPlastiC Executive Board will make the decision to approve the submission of the paper for publication or for presentation at a scientific conference. During the project EEB may adopt a series of rules that EcoPlastiC researchers should follow for knowledge management and IP protection, including those related to the publication of scientific papers.

The scientific publications plan is an integral part of the DMP, through its [Annex VI](#). It enables continuous planning and monitoring of the publication status of scientific papers planned by the project, so it will be regularly updated through another document ([Annex VII](#) - Scientific publications plan) and included in the corresponding version of DMP.

4. Allocation of resources

Human and technical resources are needed to implement the DMP presented in this document. Management of research data/outputs is an inseparable part of the research process, throughout the project, which includes the following aspects: data collection or acquisition, curation (organisation and integration of data collected from various sources), storage, (long-term) preservation, data security, quality assurance, allocation of persistent identifiers (PIDs), provision of metadata in line with disciplinary requirements, licensing, and rules and procedures for sharing data. Therefore, part of the staff costs planned in the EcoPlastiC budget will be used for the above-mentioned activities. It is clear that data/outputs management, their adaptation to FAIR principles and sharing permeate all work packages in EcoPlastiC project, not only in dedicated WP1 (Project Management) or WP6 (Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication). Even significantly greater efforts are required for data management in research work packages where a large amount of data is collected and generated.

Table 3 provides rough estimates for data management costs, per partner institutions, which include direct (staff costs expressed in PM and purchase costs in EUR) and indirect costs (related to storage, archiving, and security of data). Within WP1, a certain time is planned for monitoring of data quality, their analysis and sharing approval by EEB. Regarding the development WPs (WP2, WP3, WP4 and WP5) until 10% of the staff efforts is planned for data management during the research, for both, collected secondary and generated primary data. WP6 is specifically intended for data management, through the preparation and monitoring of DMP implementation, but also through a set of activities for data/outputs sharing through DEC (Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication) activities.

Direct purchase costs are otherwise planned in the estimated project budget, and refer to OA publishing fees, conference fees and travel costs for participation, IP protection costs and EcoPlastiC website and support costs.

Resources for long term preservation, as well as what and how data will be retained/destroyed beyond the project, will be discussed by the whole consortium during EEB meetings. Additional information regarding this will be incorporated in the next version of the DMP.

In a collaborative project like EcoPlastiC the responsibilities for data/outputs management are shared. Table 4 summarises the responsibilities of EcoPlastiC partners for data management. IMGGE as WP6 leader is responsible for overall DMP coordination, its reviewing and revision together with TUS which coordinates the whole project, as well as appointed members of EEB. Each researcher involved in the project is individually responsible for the collection, processing, and analysis of data, checking their “fairification”, as well as for the preparation of metadata in accordance with the recommendations given in this DMP, as well as disciplinary standards. WP leaders will be in charge of data quality control at a higher level for the data collected and generated within the work package they lead. The second level of final quality control will be performed by EEB members. For data storage, backup and archiving, researchers will be assisted by institutional IT teams, in charge of maintaining storage capacity. It is important to note that this applies to all research data (raw, processed), and datasets related to scientific publications that will be deposited in trusted repositories will be handled by the staff in charge of the selected repository. Regarding the sharing of data and research outputs, after analysing the limitations and approval by the EEB, the authors will be in charge of their sharing and dissemination.

Table 3 – EcoPlastiC Estimated Data Management costs

Data Management costs		TUS	AVE	NOVA	IMGGE	KTH
Direct staff costs	Staff activity	PM	PM	PM	PM	PM
WP1 - Staff costs	Monitoring of data quality EEB DM activities (approvals)	8	1	2	2	2
WP2-WP5 - Staff costs	Making data or other research outputs FAIR, Preparing scientific manuscripts, Depositing AAM/VoR and research data at trusted repositories.	8	5	10	10	5
WP6 - Staff costs	Data management activities, including DEC (dissemination, exploitation and communication) activities for data and research outputs sharing	3	2	2	5	3
Direct purchase costs	Types of purchase costs	EUR	EUR	EUR	EUR	EUR
WP6 – OA publishing	OA publishing fees	10000		10000	13000	
WP6 – Conferences	Conference fees and travel costs for participation	5000	1000	12000	7500	5000
WP6 – IP protection	IP protection costs	10000	11000			
WP6 – Website	Website and support costs				13000	
Indirect costs	Storage, archiving, security costs	16000	10000	10000	12000	10000

Table 4 – Data management responsibilities in the EcoPlastiC project

Data Management responsibilities	TUS	AVE	NOVA	IMGGE	KTH	EEB
Overall DMP coordination				WP6 leader		
Reviewing and revising DMP	Project coordinator			WP6 leader		Members
Data capture	Researchers	Researchers	Researchers	Researchers	Researchers	
Metadata production	Researchers	Researchers	Researchers	Researchers	Researchers	
Data quality assurance	WP1 leader WP2 leader researchers	WP3 leader researchers	WP4 leader researchers	WP6 leader researchers	WP5 leader researchers	Members
Storage and backup	Researchers TUS IT team	Researchers AVE IT team	Researchers NOVA IT team	Researchers IMGGE IT team	Researchers KTH IT team	
Data archiving	TUS IT team	AVE IT team	NOVA IT team	IMGGE IT team	KTH IT team	
Datasets sharing*	Authors	Authors	Authors	Authors	Authors	
Research outputs sharing*	Authors	Authors	Authors	Authors	Authors	

* Upon approval by EEB

Responsible individuals in partners' institution will be named and listed in [Annex VIII](#) of DMP. In case of replacement of named persons, this Annex will be updated, as a separate document, and incorporated in the next version of the DMP.

5. Data security

The data that will be collected and generated on the project, which includes raw, processes and analysed data will be securely stored in a decentralised manner, within partner institutional robust storage systems managed by their IT teams. Institutional storage systems should enable project researchers with quality IT services to save data, backup data, and share data with other project partners. Storing data on laptops, computers hard drives or external storage devices will be avoided even if they are encrypted.

Researchers will have the obligation to transfer collected and generated research data regularly (on a daily basis or weekly basis) to institutional storage. TUS IT teams will enable authorized access for researchers to the dedicated EcoPlastiC folder on the storage system, within which sub-folders can be structured by the researchers themselves. Such robust storage systems have automated backup, so that all data will be permanently saved and recovered in any incident events. EcoPlastiC partners will apply institutional data protection policies in addition to the provisions of the Grant Agreement during project implementation.

When researchers from several partner institutions are working on the same task, and if the internal storage capacities and procedures of a partner prevent access to project staff from other partner institutions, the data will be temporarily transferred via a secure FTP protocol, as recommended by the IT team, so that the authorised researcher could finally transfer to storage. Additional options are to temporarily use some of the recommended cloud (web-based) storage (*e.g.* Amazon Web Services, Microsoft Azure or Google Suite for Education). It should be noted that the use of Dropbox, personal Google accounts (@google.com), personal OneDrive accounts, Apple iCloud is not recommended.

Long-term preservation will be enabled for the analysed and final data, determined by the project partners, even after the duration of the project, although for some of them long-term preservation is provided by the external trusted repository where the data is deposited.

Partners who do not have storage of sufficient capacity or which is not robust as described, can purchase storage hardware during the project from the *Indirect costs* category.

Other research outputs in a digital format (shown in Table 2) will also be stored on institutional storages. Working documents (deliverables, reports *etc.*) will be stored in the EcoPlastiC repository, accessible to all members of the project team with authorised access. Research outputs that are not confidential, and that have already been published (scientific publications, patent *etc.*) will be archived on the EcoPlastiC website, which will be active for at least 7 years after the end of the project. For non-digital outputs, partner(s) who develop them will take measures for their preservation, according to good practice and institutional rules.

The storage of sensitive data related to EcoPlastiC innovation, further commercial exploitation and possible trade secrets will be specially arranged during the implementation of the project according to the recommendations of EEB members.

6. Ethics

The EcoPlastiC project was designed in such a way as to fulfil the ethical and legal requirements for the acceptance and adoption of the project results by the end users, precisely through one of the social goals SO1 (High-impact technological and scientific outcomes, compliant with legal requirements and in line with broadly shared ethical principles and values).

In terms of ethical issues, the project will be implemented in accordance with the provisions set out in the Grant Agreement and the applicable international and national laws¹⁸, as well as the highest standards of research integrity¹⁹ and information security²⁰. The relevant ethical issue to be considered for the project data is *The General Data Protection Regulation* (GDPR), *i.e.* in all situations during the project when getting personal data, and at the same time only necessary personal information to contribute to the progress of the project will be collected. Informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation will be applied when dealing with personal data. This information will be accessible only to the EcoPlastiC team members and will not be shared with any third parties. All sensitive data will be properly stored as described in Section 5.

¹⁸ EU Charter of Fundamental Rights and the European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms and its Supplementary Protocols

¹⁹ European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity

²⁰ ISO 27001-Information security management

7. Other issues

Relevant institutional, departmental or study policies on data sharing and data security are listed in the table below, per EcoPlastiC partner institution.

1. TUS

Policy	Description	URL or reference

2. AVE

Policy	Description	URL or reference
Internal data storage	Storing and sharing data internally via google drive (in the cloud).	
Back-up	Daily back-up of Google drive	
Cyber-security	Avecom has a cyber-insurance	

3. NOVA

Policy	Description	URL or reference
Pure - Research Information Management System	PURE is NOVA's Current Research Information System (CRIS). Information held in PURE relates to research staff and their publications and activities information. The system allows for relationships and associations to be created between research inputs and outputs, providing a broad picture of research activity at individual, department, research unit, academic unit and University levels.	https://www.unl.pt/sites/default/files/gestao_de_informacao_cientifica_nova_site_v3.pdf

4. IMGGE

Policy	Description	URL or reference
Internal data storage	Local NAS (Network Attached Storage) for storage data and a configured RAID (Redundant Array of Independent Disks) system to increase reliability of data storage.	
Back-up	Dedicated local hard disks for periodical backups (automatically, by our scripts).	

Data sharing	For exchanging files with other institutions, we use our SFTP (Secure File Transfer Protocol) server protected by usual security standards.	
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5. KTH

Policy	Description	URL or reference
<p>For data sharing: KTH OneDrive</p> <p>For data storage:</p> <p>“If you need to store data confined by secrecy/restricted data or more than 20000 files you can contact the KTH IT department.”</p>	<p>Storing and sharing data are separate processes. Many data repositories allow for storage up to a certain limit. For larger datasets, there are options available for researchers at KTH</p>	<p>https://www.kth.se/en/biblioteket/publicera-analysera/hantera-forskningsdata/lagring-av-forskningsdata-och-langsiktigt-bevarande-1.861129</p> <p>“Contact the Research data team. We can help you with various questions about research data, from planning to publishing.”</p> <p>Email: researchdata@kth.se</p>
For sensitive data	Recommendations for working with sensitive data	<p>https://www.kth.se/en/biblioteket/publicera-analysera/hantera-forskningsdata/rekommendationer-vid-arbete-med-kansliga-data-1.1125398</p>

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Annex I – EcoPlastiC datasets

No	Dataset title	WP	Responsible partner	Short description	Format	Open access	Closed /Restricted	Repository/ PID
						License (CC BY or CC0)	Justification	
1	Identification aerobic isolates capable of degrading depolymerized plastic mixtures and monomers	3	AVE	Evaluation and development of AVE's working microbiomes and a biobank for single isolates dedicated to waste plastic monomer degradation and bioconversión for high PHA and other useful products	docx, xlsx, ppt, png	No	Restricted due to IP protection (trade secret, patent <i>etc.</i>)	
2	Enrichment of anaerobic microbiomes for methane production using depolymerized mixed plastic waste	3	AVE	Green depolymerisation products and residual products after aerobic fermentation will be used to enrich anaerobic microbiomes and to monitor their bioconversion capacities in relation to the subsequent biomethane	docs, xlsx, ppt	No	Restricted due to IP protection (trade secret, patent <i>etc.</i>)	
3	Microbial combination assembly for degradation and conversion of depolymerized plastic mixtures and monomers	3	AVE	Optimization of the microbiome composition to achieve desired degradation and high bioconversion of PHA/biogas	docx, xlsx, ppt	No	Restricted due to IP protection (trade secret, patent <i>etc.</i>)	
4	Evolution of process performance of microbial consortium	3	AVE	Optimization growth conditions (pH, EC, temperature, DO) to achieve the highest degradation and conversion capabilities during different aerobic and anaerobic batch fermentation	docx, xlsx, ppt, png	No	Restricted due to IP protection (trade secret, patent <i>etc.</i>)	

5	Aerobic and anaerobic microbiome composition	3	AVE	Determination of microbiome composition using next generation sequencing to verify the overall stability of microbiome	docx, ppt, fastq	No	Restricted due to IP protection (trade secret, patent <i>etc.</i>)	
6	Validation of best-performing microbial communities for biopolymer production	3	AVE	Validation of the optimized microbiomes during different batch, fed-batch and continuous fermentation experiments under different operational parameters	docxd, xlsx, ppt, png	No	Restricted due to IP protection (trade secret, patent <i>etc.</i>)	
7	Aerobic PHA production	4	Nova	Identification of the most optimal process parameters for the technical scale PHA production.	docx, xlsx, ppt, png	No	Restricted due to IP protection (trade secret, patent <i>etc.</i>)	
8								
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15								

Annex II – FAIR Checklist

Dataset/files

- Is the dataset in an open & trusted repository (if available)?
- Does the dataset have a registered DOI?
- Are data files in standard and/or commonly available open formats (as much as possible)?
- Are the data and/or metadata retrievable via an API and/or discoverable through an open search protocol?

README/metadata

- Are all associated data files unambiguously named in the metadata and described including file types, software requirements and/or conversion information?
- Does the metadata include useful disciplinary notation and terminology? (*e.g.*, SI units, common domain identifiers, explain acronyms, define field-specific jargon)
- Does the metadata include machine-readable standards where available (*e.g.* ORCiDs for authors and/or data contributors)
- Are related articles referenced and linked in the metadata?
- Is a citation format for the dataset provided?
- Are any license terms, attribution, or terms of use clearly indicated?
- Is the metadata exportable in a machine-readable structured text-based format? (*e.g.*, XML, JSON)

Additional tips for preparing your data for sharing

Preparing your data files:

- You may choose to include raw data (as originally collected), processed data (*e.g.*, signals encoded), or both. The decision depends on what is most useful or common in a discipline or specifically required by a publisher or repository
- Use file formats that are common and open as much as possible, including for discipline-specific data types if open formats are available
- Use unambiguous filenames and organise the files logically according to your project (*e.g.*, by sample, treatment, method, *etc.*)

Documenting your data and files:

- For an easy, low-barrier approach, use a README template and save as a plain text document (.txt). Note that some repositories may provide specific documentation templates.
- List the data files included in the package, and/or describe the file naming schema and organisation. Include their formats and any specific software requirements and/or conversion information if you have it.
- Describe methods of data collection and file structures and organisation including useful notation about the data headers, units, sample identifiers, *etc.* Use standard or conventional terminology or nomenclature in your discipline.
- Reference associated articles, code and related datasets. Include ORCiDs of all data contributors.

Depositing your data in a repository:

- Select a reputable data repository and upload dataset (publishers or funders may require specific repositories; many domain-specific repositories provide enhanced services and curation for specific data types)
- Make sure the repository provides a persistent identifier (*e.g.*, DOI, handle, or other) and specifies conditions for others to access and re-use the data (such as a public domain declaration or Creative Commons attribution license; licensing policy may vary by repository)
- Provide a pre-formatted citation (and license attribution if appropriate) for the dataset on your website and other materials so users can easily copy and attribute; for example:
 - Author(s). Dataset Title, Version. Data Repository (or Journal if appropriate). Year. DOI. (Date accessed)
 - [License attribution if appropriate.]

Annex III – Recommended and selected repositories and databases

Recommended repositories and databases:

- **Zenodo** - a general-purpose open research data repository for the preservation and making available of research, educational and informational content, built and developed by OpenAIRE and CERN (<https://zenodo.org/>)
- **Figshare** - repository where researchers can make all of their research outputs available in a citable, shareable and discoverable manner (<https://figshare.com/>)
- **Dryad Data Platform** - general-purpose open source platform for data publication and digital preservation of a wide diversity of data types, in underlying repository with which it is integrated (<https://datadryad.org/stash>)
- **EUDAT** - Collaborative Data Infrastructure (or EUDAT CDI) is one of the largest infrastructures of integrated data services and resources supporting research in Europe (<https://www.eudat.eu/>)
- **Dataverse** – available as an open source web application to share, preserve, cite, explore, and analyse research data, developed by the Institute for Quantitative Social Science (IQSS) in collaboration with the Harvard University (<https://dataverse.org/>)
- **ELIXIR** – coordinates and develops life science resources across Europe so that researchers can more easily find, analyse and share data, exchange expertise, and implement best practices (<https://elixir-europe.org/platforms/data/elixir-deposition-databases>)
- **PAZy** - The Plastics-Active Enzymes Database - database that lists exclusively biochemically characterised plastic-active enzymes (<https://pazy.eu/doku.php>)
- **GenBank database** – a part of the International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration database, designed to provide and encourage access within the scientific community to the most up-to-date and comprehensive DNA sequence information (<https://ftp.ncbi.nih.gov/genbank/>)

Selected trusted repositories (to be defined in the first year of the EcoPlastiC project):

Selected databases (to be defined in the first year of the EcoPlastiC project):

Annex IV – Disciplinary metadata standards relevant for EcoPlastiC

Source: *Metada data standards catalogue* (<https://rdamsc.bath.ac.uk/subject-index>)

Materials engineering

[CIF \(Crystallographic Information Framework\)](#) - A well-established standard file structure for the archiving and distribution of crystallographic information, CIF is in regular use for reporting crystal structure determinations to Acta Crystallographica and other journals.

[CSMD \(Core Scientific Metadata Model\)](#) - A study-data oriented model, primarily in support of the ICAT data management infrastructure software. The CSMD is designed to support data collected within a large-scale facility's scientific workflow; however the model is also designed to be generic across scientific disciplines.

[EngMeta](#) - EngMeta is an XML-based formal definition of information necessary to find, understand, reproduce and reuse data from engineering disciplines. The schema was defined together with engineers from aerodynamics and thermodynamics and lies a focus on computational engineering, but is general enough to cover other engineering disciplines. It is based on existing standards like DataCite, PREMIS, CodeMeta and ExptML and is implemented as two metadata blocks for repositories based on the open-source repository platform Dataverse.

[NeXus](#) - NeXus is an international standard for the storage and exchange of neutron, X-ray, and muon experiment data. The structure of NeXus files is extremely flexible, allowing the storage of both simple data sets, such as a single data array and its axes, and highly complex data and their associated metadata, such as measurements on a multi-component instrument or numerical simulations. NeXus is built on top of the container format HDF5, and adds domain-specific rules for organizing data within HDF5 files in addition to a dictionary of well-defined domain-specific field names.

Biochemistry

[CSMD \(Core Scientific Metadata Model\)](#) - A study-data oriented model, primarily in support of the ICAT data management infrastructure software. The CSMD is designed to support data collected within a large-scale facility's scientific workflow; the model is also designed to be generic across scientific disciplines.

[DIF \(Directory Interchange Format\)](#) - An early metadata initiative from the Earth sciences community, intended for the description of scientific data sets. It includes elements focusing on instruments that capture data, temporal and spatial characteristics of the data, and projects with which the dataset is associated. It is defined as a W3C XML Schema.

[FGDC/CSDGM \(Federal Geographic Data Committee Content Standard for Digital Geospatial Metadata\)](#) - A widely-used, but no longer current standard defining the information content for a set of digital geospatial data required by the US Federal Government.

[ISA-Tab](#) - The Investigation/Study/Assay (ISA) tab-delimited (TAB) format is a general purpose framework with which to collect and communicate complex metadata (*i.e.* sample characteristics, technologies used, type of measurements made) from 'omics-based' experiments employing a combination of technologies.

[MIBBI \(Minimum Information for Biological and Biomedical Investigations\)](#) - A common portal to a group of nearly 40 checklists of Minimum Information for various biological disciplines. The MIBBI Foundry is developing a cross-analysis of these guidelines to create an intercompatible, extensible community of standards. The concept was realised initially through the joint efforts of the Proteomics Standards Initiative, the Genomic Standards Consortium and the MGED RSBI Working Groups.

[Minimum Information about any \(x\) Sequence \(MIxS\)](#) - MIxS currently consists of three separate checklists; MIGS for genomes, MIMS for metagenomes, and MIMARKS for marker genes. To create a single entry point to all minimum information checklists from the GSC and to the environmental packages, we created an overarching framework, the MIxS standard (publication in Nature Biotechnology). MIxS includes the technology-specific checklists from the previous MIGS and MIMS standards, provides a way of introducing additional checklists such as MIMARKS, and also allows annotation of sample data using environmental packages.

[Repository - Developed Metadata Schemas](#) - Some repositories have decided that current standards do not fit their metadata needs, and so have created their own requirements.

[SNRNASM ISA-Tab](#) - An ISA-Tab-based standard for reporting the results of single nucleotide resolution nucleic acid structure mapping experiments.

Molecular biology

[ISA-Tab](#) - The Investigation/Study/Assay (ISA) tab-delimited (TAB) format is a general purpose framework with which to collect and communicate complex metadata (*i.e.* sample characteristics, technologies used, type of measurements made) from 'omics-based' experiments employing a combination of technologies.

[Minimum Information about any \(x\) Sequence \(MIxS\)](#) - MIxS currently consists of three separate checklists; MIGS for genomes, MIMS for metagenomes, and MIMARKS for marker genes. To create a single entry point to all minimum information checklists from the GSC and to the environmental packages, we created an overarching framework, the MIxS standard (publication in Nature Biotechnology). MIxS includes the technology-specific checklists from the previous MIGS and MIMS standards, provides a way of introducing additional checklists such as MIMARKS, and also allows annotation of sample data using environmental packages.

[PDBx/mmCIF \(Protein Data Bank Exchange Dictionary and the Macromolecular Crystallographic Information Framework\)](#) - Protein Data Bank archive (PDB) is the single worldwide archival repository of information about the 3D structures of proteins, nucleic acids, and complex assemblies, managed by the Worldwide PDB (wwPDB). The PDB Exchange Dictionary (PDBx) is used by the wwPDB to define data content for deposition, annotation and archiving of PDB entries. PDBx incorporates the community standard metadata representation, the Macromolecular Crystallographic Information Framework (mmCIF), originally developed under the auspices of the International Union of Crystallography (IUCr). PDBx has been extended by the wwPDB to include descriptions of other experimental methods that

produce 3D macromolecular structure models such as Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Spectroscopy, 3D Electron Microscopy and Tomography.

[Repository-Developed Metadata Schemas](#) - Some repositories have decided that current standards do not fit their metadata needs, and so have created their own requirements.

Ecological balance

[ABCD \(Access to Biological Collection Data\)](#) - The Access to Biological Collections Data (ABCD) Schema is an evolving comprehensive standard for the access to and exchange of data about specimens and observations (a.k.a. primary biodiversity data). The ABCD Schema attempts to be comprehensive and highly structured, supporting data from a wide variety of databases. It is compatible with several existing data standards. Parallel structures exist so that either (or both) atomised data and free-text can be accommodated.

[Darwin Core](#) - A body of standards, including a glossary of terms (in other contexts these might be called properties, elements, fields, columns, attributes, or concepts) intended to facilitate the sharing of information about biological diversity by providing reference definitions, examples, and commentaries.

[EML \(Ecological Metadata Language\)](#) - Ecological Metadata Language (EML) is a metadata specification particularly developed for the ecology discipline. It is based on prior work done by the Ecological Society of America and associated efforts (Michener et al., 1997, Ecological Applications).

[GBIF Metadata Profile](#) - Established by a global network of countries and organisations, GBIF is a web portal promoting and facilitating the mobilisation, access, discovery and use of biodiversity data. The portal uses a profile of EML; a [How-to Guide](#) and [Reference Guide](#) for using the profile are available.

[Minimum Information about any \(x\) Sequence \(MIxS\)](#) - MIxS currently consists of three separate checklists; MIGS for genomes, MIMS for metagenomes, and MIMARKS for marker genes. To create a single entry point to all minimum information checklists from the GSC and to the environmental packages, we created an overarching framework, the MIxS standard (publication in Nature Biotechnology). MIxS includes the technology-specific checklists from the previous MIGS and MIMS standards, provides a way of introducing additional checklists such as MIMARKS, and also allows annotation of sample data using environmental packages.

[UKEOF](#) - A metadata standard for describing environmental monitoring activities, programmes, networks and facilities published by the UK Environmental Observation Framework (UKEOF).

Annex V – Proposed “readme” style of metadata

Source: <https://cornell.app.box.com/v/ReadmeTemplate>

This readme file was generated on [YYYY-MM-DD] by [NAME]

GENERAL INFORMATION

Title of Dataset:

Author/Principal Investigator Information

Name:

ORCID:

Institution:

Address:

Email:

Author/Associate or Co-Investigator Information

Name:

ORCID:

Institution:

Address:

Email:

<repeat this section for other authors, as appropriate>

Date of data collection:

<provide single date, range, or approximate date; suggested format YYYY-MM-DD>

Geographic location of data collection:

<provide latitude, longitude, or city/region, State, Country>

Information about funding sources that supported the collection of the data:

SHARING/ACCESS INFORMATION

Licenses/restrictions placed on the data:

Links to publications that cite or use the data:

Links to other publicly accessible locations of the data:

Links/relationships to ancillary data sets:

Was data derived from another source?

If yes, list source(s):

Recommended citation for this dataset:

DATA & FILE OVERVIEW

File List:

<list all files (or folders, as appropriate for dataset organisation) contained in the dataset, with a brief description>

Relationship between files, if important:

Additional related data collected that was not included in the current data package:

Are there multiple versions of the dataset?

If yes, name of file(s) that was updated:

Why was the file updated?

When was the file updated?

METHODOLOGICAL INFORMATION

Description of methods used for collection/generation of data:

<include links or references to publications or other documentation containing experimental design or protocols used in data collection>

Methods for processing the data:

<describe how the submitted data were generated from the raw or collected data>

Instrument- or software-specific information needed to interpret the data:

<include full name and version of software, and any necessary packages or libraries needed to run scripts>

Standards and calibration information, if appropriate:

Environmental/experimental conditions:

Describe any quality-assurance procedures performed on the data:

People involved with sample collection, processing, analysis and/or submission:

DATA-SPECIFIC INFORMATION FOR: [FILENAME]

<repeat this section for each dataset, folder or file, as appropriate>

Number of variables:

Number of cases/rows:

Variable List:

<list variable name(s), description(s), unit(s) and value labels as appropriate for each>

Missing data codes:

<list code/symbol and definition>

Specialised formats or other abbreviations used:

Annex VI – Data availability statement examples

Case	Statement example
Data are openly available in a repository	“Data supporting this study are openly available from (NAME OF REPOSITORY) at (DOI, ACCESSION NUMBER OR URL)”
Data are available in a repository, but subject to an embargo	“Data supporting this study will be available from (NAME OF REPOSITORY) at (DOI, ACCESSION NUMBER OR URL) following a 6 month embargo”
Data are available in a repository, but access is restricted due to legal, ethical or commercial reasons	“Data supporting this study are available from (NAME OF REPOSITORY) at (DOI, ACCESSION NUMBER OR URL). Access to the data is subject to approval and a data sharing agreement due to (GIVE REASONS WHY ACCESS TO THE DATA IS RESTRICTED)”
Secondary analysis of third party data subject to restrictions	“This study used third party data made available under licence that the author does not have permission to share. Requests to access the data should be directed to (THIRD PARTY) at (URL/CONTACT DETAILS)”
Data available as supplementary information	“Data supporting this study are included within the article and/or supporting materials”
Data are available on request only due to ethical, legal or commercial reasons*	“Data supporting this study are not publicly available due to (GIVE REASONS WHY DATA ARE NOT PUBLIC). Please contact (GIVE EMAIL ADDRESS)”
Data cannot be shared due to ethical, legal or commercial restrictions**	“Data supporting this study cannot be made available due to (GIVE REASONS WHY THE DATA CANNOT BE SHARED)”
No new data generated or analysed	“No new data were generated or analysed during this study”

*A simple direction to contact the author may not be considered acceptable by some funders and publishers. Consider setting up a shared email address for your research group or use an existing departmental address.

** Under some circumstances (*e.g.* participants did not agree for their data to be shared) it may be appropriate to explain that the data are not available at all. In this case, you must give clear and justified reasons.

Annex VII – EcoPlastiC scientific publications plan

No	Publication title	WP	Publishing option*	Journal title	OA repository	EEB approval date	Submission Due date	Publishing status**
1								
2								
3								
4								
5								
6								
7								
8								
9								
10								
11								
12								

* Green OA, Gold OA, Diamond OA, Hybrid journal, Sister journal, Subscription journal

** DM – Draft Manuscript (waiting for EEB approval)

SM – Submitted manuscript

AAM – Author Accepted Manuscript

VoR – Version of Record (published)

Annex VIII – Responsible persons for EcoPlastiC data management

Due to the protection of personal data, this Annex is different in the public version of the DMP. Rows can be added to the tables below as needed.

1. TUS

Data Management responsibilities	Roles	Responsible person(s) name(s)	Email(s)	Contact(s)	Address(es)	EEB member(s) names
Reviewing and revising DMP	Project coordinator					<i>Member</i>
Data quality assurance	WP1 leader WP2 leader					<i>Member</i>
Storage and backup	TUS IT team					
Data archiving	TUS IT team					

2. AVE

Data Management responsibilities	Roles	Responsible person(s) name(s)	Email(s)	Contact(s)	Address(es)	EEB member(s) names
Reviewing and revising DMP	WP3 leader	Zahra Geraylou				<i>Member</i>
Data quality assurance	WP3 leader	Zahra Geraylou				
Storage and backup	AVE IT team	Stijn Boeren				Deputy member
Data archiving	AVE IT team	Stijn Boeren				Deputy member

3. NOVA

Data Management responsibilities	Roles	Responsible person(s) name(s)	Email(s)	Contact(s)	Address(es)	EEB member(s) names
Reviewing and revising DMP		Bárbara Almeida Patrícia Concórdio-Reis				<i>Member</i>

Data quality assurance	WP4 leader	Filomena Freitas				<i>Member</i>
Storage and backup	Researcher	Patrícia Concórdio-Reis				
Data archiving	Researcher	Patrícia Concórdio-Reis				

4. IMGGE

Data Management responsibilities	Roles	Responsible person(s) name(s)	Email(s)	Contact(s)	Address(es)	EEB member(s) names
Overall DMP coordination	WP6 leader	Jasmina Nikodinovic-Runic				
Reviewing and revising DMP	WP6 leader	Jasmina Nikodinovic-Runic				<i>Member</i>
Data quality assurance	WP6 leader	Jasmina Nikodinovic-Runic				<i>Member</i>
Storage and backup	IMGGE IT team	Nikola Ilic				
Data archiving	IMGGE IT team	Nikola Ilic				

5. KTH

Data Management responsibilities	Roles	Responsible person(s) name(s)	Email(s)	Contact(s)	Address(es)	EEB member(s) names
Data quality assurance	WP5 leader	Kiran Reddy Baddigam				<i>Member</i>
Storage and backup	KTH IT team	Kjell Agnekil				
Data archiving	KTH IT team	Kjell Agnekil				